

Speculative future university 2050

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Speculating and imagining more hopeful learning futures can spark change (Houlden & Veletsianos, 2023). With academic–professional boundaries blurring and third space practitioner (TSP) roles such as learning designers, academic developers and education designers becoming more fluid and dynamic (Whitchurch, 2018), speculative activities offer TSPs ways to play with possible futures and anticipate and lean into how their roles might evolve.

In this activity, we invited TSPs to explore speculative future scenarios in higher education. This online, asynchronous activity invited participants to imagine how higher education institutions (HEIs) might change and/or stay the same from a TSP point of view. Through the looking glass of a shared whiteboard space, participants speculated on potential new roles for TSPs such as near-future learning designers (Costello et al., 2022), joys and frustrations, and anticipating challenges and new directions for education.

The task

Imagine you are transported to the year 2050. How would your role change? Where would you be working? What are the joys and frustrations of TSPs in this future? To capture these speculations, an online whiteboard space offered three provocations.

Provocations for the future

We seeded the online whiteboards with our own provocations.

Provocation 1: Future university?

Our first speculation about the “Future University” prompted the most conversation and reaction. AI-generated images were uploaded for comment and deconstruction.

Microsoft Copilot’s sleek, corporate-utopian campus (Figure 1) is an unsettling classroom scene featuring sensory manipulation technology and students with raised hands in what feels more like operant conditioning and Audrey Watters’ “teaching machines” than education. The image shows there is clearly more work to be done to imagine educational futures that both embrace technology and avoid its potentially dehumanising and negative environmental aspects.

Figure 1

Another AI-generated image shared (Figure 2) depicts a sleek, futuristic university campus with flowing organic architecture, extensive green spaces and gardens, holographic displays, and autonomous vehicles, representing another corporate vision of 2050 education where advanced technology is seamlessly integrated with environmental sustainability in a polished, optimised setting. Green spaces may well be essential for both environmental cooling and psychological grounding in a tech-heavy 2050 university. There was a sense that the gardens we need in 2050 need cultivating today.

Figure 2

Provocation 2: How does technology impact your work? Potential joys or frustrations?

Our second provocation for 2050 third spacers was: How does technology impact your work? AI's role in transforming instructional design? The facilitators of this speculation reflected on the

pragmatic approach of using technology to amplify rather than replace human expertise in educational design. Human skills may become more valuable as technology handles routine tasks, although we retain healthy scepticism about ensuring quality outcomes and educational purpose.

The aspects of joy and frustrations were also part of this provocation. Third spacers currently struggle with workload and professional recognition in higher education is a volatile space. Now and into the future these aspects can be seen as causing much frustration and disruption.

Provocation 3: What is the student experience in 2050?

The future student experience could become globally networked and hyper-personalised, with learners curating credentials from any institution worldwide. We are seeing a messy future despite AI's smooth promises.

Reflection

Would we do it again? We found the speculation an interesting exercise. Including synchronous sessions and real-time interaction could potentially extend the speculation. Experimenting more with the process and the duration of the workshop, to allow time for the development of personas, might help reflect more hopes and anxieties about education and student experience in 2050.

References

- Costello, E., Welsh, S., Girme, P., Concannon, F., Farrelly, T., & Thompson, C. (2023). Who cares about learning design? Near future superheroes and villains of an educational ethics of care. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 48(3), 460–475.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2022.2074452>
- Houlden, S., & Veletsianos, G. (2023). Impossible dreaming: On speculative education fiction and hopeful learning futures. *Postdigital Science and Education*, 5(3), 605–622.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s42438-022-00348-7>
- Watters, A. (2023). *Teaching machines: The history of personalized learning*. MIT Press.
- Whitchurch, C. (2018). Being a higher education professional today: Working in a third space. In C. Bossu & N. Brown (Eds.), *Professional and support staff in higher education* (pp. 11–21). Springer Nature.

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